

An Empirical Study on NEP 2020 with Special Reference to Measure its Awareness Among Academicians and Students

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Abstract

Change is Universal, it is quite essential for the progressive society and so is important for the education sector. An all-inclusive and comprehensive framework was need of an hour for the transformation of our education system, which can be achieved by putting efforts towards adopting updated learning methodology an advance learning process in the form of discussion and analysis-based learning rather than the content based. The National Education Policy 2020 is designed by integrating both traditional and modern education system from elementary education to higher and vocational training. While The NEP has revised the pedagogical structure in an effort to attain cognitive development and ensure quality education for all. There has been quite a high expectations from NEP among educationist, academicians and students, since the NEP has now been implemented nationwide in this paper author is going to explore about its awareness among academicians and students and measure their level of acquaintances related to each aspect of NEP draft. An extensive survey in the form of questionnaire from various academicians has been conducted to analyse and evaluate the same.

Keywords NEP, Pedagogical Structure, Cognitive Development, Elementary Education.

Introduction

It has replaced the previous National policy on Education 1986. The policy is a result of an extensive study to provide in all-inclusive framework for Primary education to higher as well as vocational training in both rural and urban India. The aim of the policy is to transform India's education system by the year 2030.

In the year 1950 a planning commission was appointed to frame the blueprint of different aspects of life including education. In 1961, the Union government formed the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) as an autonomous organisation that would advise both the Union and state governments on formulating and implementing education policies.

The Kothari Commission was formed by Govt of India on 14th July 1964 in order to review the present state of education system then that commission consisted of twenty members who were the experts of U.K, Japan, Sweden and France. The result of the commission concluded that Indian education system did not prepare the learners for their career path and the change is needed for the future improvement.

In order to understand India's new education Policy 2020. We must first go through the history of Indian education system post-independence. Understand the national policy on education 1986. In the year (1964 – 66), University Grants Commission and the Kothari Commission developed the proposals to modernise India's education system..

The National Policy on Education (NPE) was adopted by Parliament in May 1986. A committee was set up under the chairmanship of Acharya Ramamurti in May 1990 to review NPE and to make recommendations for its modifications. That Committee submitted its report in December 1990. ³

A committee was set up in July 1991 under the chairmanship of Shri N. Janardhana Reddy, Chief Minister of Andhra Pradesh, to make recommendations regarding modifications to be made in the NPE on the basis of the recommendation of the committee.

Under the National Policy on Education (NPE), 1986 envisaged to conduct of a common entrance examination on all India basis for technical education. Three – Exam Scheme (JEE and AIEEE at the National Level and the State Level Engineering Entrance Examinations (SLEEE) for State Level Institutions with an option to join AIEEE).

After long gap of 34 years in the year 2019, the then Ministry of Human Resource Development and now the Ministry of Education released a Draft New Education Policy 2019, which was followed by a number of public consultations.

Objective of study

1. To examine the set goals of the policy.
2. To check the awareness of people towards the NEP proposals.
3. To evaluate its implementation and execution plan.
4. To recommend any improvement required to strengthen the policy.

Review of Literature

1. An Empirical Study on NEP 2020 [National Education Policy] with Special Reference to the Future of Indian Education System and Its effects on the Stakeholders: JMEIT

It is an empirical study on the National Education Policy 2020 and its effects on the Indian education system and its stakeholders. The author conducted a survey of 1000 respondents, including students, parents, teachers, and educationalists, to assess their awareness and opinions on the NEP 2020. empirical study on the National Education Policy 2020 and its effects on the Indian education system and its stakeholders. The author conducted a survey of 1000 respondents, including students, parents, teachers, and educationalists, to assess their awareness and opinions on the NEP 2020.

2. Venkateshwarlu, B. (2021). A critical study of NEP 2020: Issues, approaches, challenges, opportunities and criticism. Peer Reviewed and Refereed Journal, 10(2), 1-10.

3. Kumar, A. (2021). New education policy (NEP) 2020: A roadmap for India 2.0. In W. B. James, C. Cobanoglu, & M. Cavusoglu (Eds.), Advances in global education and research (Vol. 4, pp. 1–8). USF M3 Publishing.

4. International Journal of Business and Management Research. (n.d.). Submit article. Retrieved from <https://ijbmr.forexjournal.co.in/submit-article.php>

This article analyzes the NEP 2020 and its impact on higher education in India. It also discusses the challenges and opportunities of implementing the policy, such as the funding, infrastructure, teacher training, and digital divide. The article suggests that the NEP 2020 is a step in the right direction, but its success will depend on the government's ability to address the hurdles of implementation.

- Hypothesis**
- Ho- More than 50% of the people are not aware about the NEP proposals.
H1- More than 50% of the people are aware about the NEP Proposals.

Methodology

Since this is an empirical study, the data collection sources are Primary and secondary and has been collected from Govt website, published articles etc.

Survey method was used to conduct the study by the set of questionnaire comprised of demographic dividend and general awareness about draft of NEP 2020.

Sampling

A random sampling was conducted in an University and a total sample size was 30 in which 21 respondents participated in the survey and completed the questionnaire.

Significance of the study

1. This study holds significance as it would help to understand the major highlights of the NEP 2020.

2. It would also provide an insight into the basic awareness level of the NEP drafts among the academicians and students.
3. An important steps at the University or school level can be taken to educate the people about its major highlights and about its implementation programs in the coming years.
4. Importance of formative years- Recognising the importance of formative years the policy has made provisions for the necessary learning condition like nutritious food and experts in various discipline.
5. Vocational courses in school curriculum – Introduction of vocational courses to the school curriculum will encourage the disadvantaged sections to add value in the education.
6. Universal education- expansion of the universal education from the age of 6- 14 years to 3- 18 years has been the remarkable step in the education system.
7. Three language formula – The suggestion has been made to teach in 3 languages mother tongue / local languages, which has made this policy different from all the previous amendments. This will help in breaking the illogical hysteria towards English medium schools.
8. Recognition of socio-economically backward areas – The need of such communities have been recognised and its inclusion in the main stream has been the most important steps taken for over all development of the society.

Analysis

1. Approval- It has been approved by the Union Cabinet of India on July 28th 2020.

It aims to provide flexibility in the curriculum, focus on vocational training with internships during the school, it also promotes the use of technology in education, and ensure continuous teacher training and professional development. Ever since it has released, it has become the debatable topic among stakeholders, some finds it a major reform and some are raising concerns about its implementation.

2. Approach- This policy has a very clear vision i.e transforming the Indian traditional rote- learning education approach to the cognitive and analytical based learning . It facilitates skill development and creativity.

3. Early child care and education –A research states that over 85% of a child's cumulative brain development occurs prior to the age of 6. Acknowledging the same it is ensured under the policy that healthy brain development and growth would be the prime focus and hence the current form of 10+2 structure is planned to be transformed to new 5+3+3+4 structure so the early childhood care is implemented from the age of 3 years.

4. Foundational literacy- There has been a various reports published, that states there are large no of students who have not attended foundational literacy and numeracy. The Priority of the education system is to achieve universal foundational literacy and numeracy in primary school by 2025 and for which A National Curricular and Pedagogical Framework for Early Childhood Care and Education (NCFECCE) will be developed by NCERT in two parts (0-3 and 3-8).⁴

5. Pupil teacher Ratio- The (PTR) will be kept under 30:1 at the level of each school and 25:1 for socio-economically backward areas. In addition to midday meals a nutritious and energising breakfast will be provided for productive study of cognitive subject.

6. Improving GER(Gross enrolment ratio)– There has been a significant amount of drop out after Grade 5 and Grade 8 as per the report which has deprived the previous policy to attain its set goals, this policy targets to achieve 100% Gross Enrolment Ratio in preschool to secondary level by 2030.

7. Holistic approach– Students will be offered a wide choice of subjects and discipline, the progress card will be redesigned with 360 degree approach, which would reflect the uniqueness of each students.

8. Higher education- Higher education plays a very prominent role in human development as a whole. It contributes towards sustainable livelihoods as India moves towards a knowledge economy, higher education aspirants will increase in numbers.

There has been a major problems in our existing policy and hence NEP has brought various reforms by ending the fragmentation of higher education and transforming higher education institutions into large multidisciplinary universities, colleges, and HEI clusters with the aim of having 3000 students each.

The undergraduate degree will be of 3 or 4-year duration, with multiple exit options within this period, with appropriate certifications with the digital establishment of ABC (Academic Bank Credit)

1. Socio-economically disadvantaged group (SEDGs)- The major attraction of the policy is the inclusion of disadvantaged groups such as transgenders, in order to enhance the gender balance, an appropriate fund is allotted for the education to such groups.

2. Minimum qualification- By 2030, the minimal degree qualification for school teachers would be the 4-year integrated B.Ed. offered by multidisciplinary HEIs.

3. Higher Education Commission of India (HECI)- Under this policy government's move is to set up the Higher Education Commission of India (HECI) as a single umbrella body for the entire higher education (excluding medical and legal education). Both private and public higher education institutions will be governed by the same set of norms for regulation, accreditation and academic standards.⁵

Challenges to be faced by NEP 2020

With various opportunity comes different challenges which needs to be addressed on priority basis to achieve the set goals.

1. The insufficient teachers training institutions in the country can impose a major challenge in successful implementation of the policy as the institutes which is presently running is for profit motive and is insufficient to cater the needs of quality teachers training.

2. To break the monopoly of the English medium and coaching classes culture is not the easy task specially where education has been commercialised till such an extent , it will require lots of effort and political will.

3. The policy is criticised for no exam till 7th and 8th std which will result to the no outcome of the learnings , and it can prove to be the major drawback of the policy.⁶

4. The introduction of the free breakfast will add on extra fiscal burden on the government who is already facing the issues with inefficient mid-day meal scheme.

5. The increase in the budget spent on education to 6 % of the GDP might not be as effective as there has been an increase demand for budget expenditure on defence and other sectors too. The previous commission on education had also failed to achieve the set target.

6. The gap between the skills and knowledge imparted and the job availability will pose a potent challenge specially when we are in the era of Artificial Intelligence .¹

Data analysis and Interpretation

As per the survey Data was collected on the basis of the responses collected on the various questions put up in the questionnaire.

Demographic and personal Information

1.

2) Gender
21 responses

The survey was conducted in which total of 33.3% male and 66.7% Female had participated to answer the NEP related awareness question. Total responses collected was 21, that shows people has been quite not interested in the survey even after belonging to the academic field, which clearly is not a good sign.

2. Age group

3) Age
21 responses

Maximum participants in the survey belongs to the age group of 29 years to 39 years which accounts for 42.9%, where as 38 % falls under the age group of 18 years to 28 years followed by 19% of the participants fall under 39 and above category. That shows most of the youngsters were covered in the survey and their participation shows there participation shows, they have been quite enthusiastic about the New policies related to the education.

3. Education

Maximum participants that is 47.6 % was post Doctorate, 33.3% was graduate and 14.3% belonged to the other professional courses. As the researcher expected to get the Maximum participants from the Doctorate and post Doctorate category which is an essential elements of this awareness research.

4. Awareness about new Education Policy

When asked about if they are aware about the New education Policy and have heard about it, majority of them that is 95.2 % participants were aware about the implementation of the NEP. Which is quite a positive response.

5. NEP system

When asked about the new system which has replaced the old one almost 81% of the participants answers the question correctly, which is quite satisfactory as it states that people are well versed with the most basic foundation of the policy.

6. When asked about std from which the vocational course is introduced.

Only 42.9% of the participants could only answer it correct, which means most of the people who belong to the education sector has not read the draft completely and is less informed, that certainly put question on their zeal to be updated, and their least interest in its significance and importance.

7. When asked about the stages at which student assessment is proposed in the new policy.

Only 47.6% of the participants could give the correct answer, which is again a disappointment as these were the major highlights in the NEP and is expected to be known by the post Doctorate candidates. Also its unawareness raises question on their assessment mechanism if the NEP has been implemented in the institute.

8. Question on Pupil Teacher ratio in the proposed NEP.

52.4% participants could give the correct ratio, rest had two different options which was again not satisfying while measuring the awareness, as such question forms a part of general awareness to the participants who belongs to the education sector.

9. Target of achieving the Gross enrolment ratio by which year

Only 57% of participants could give correct answer, which was expected to be known by maximum participants as by far many seminars have been conducted on the same on various platforms. That shows respondents have less access or less motivation towards attending the National and International Seminars on the current issues.

Hypothesis testing

Two samples Fishers t- test is applied

Male- 15

Female- 6

Sample 1 Population mean = 50 % which is 9

Sample 2 population mean = 50% which is 6

Assumed population mean

Table 1.1

	Total population	Population Mean
Male	15	9
Female	06	6

Table 1.2

	Sample Mean	S.D	Sample Variance	Calculated value t - test	Degree of Freedom	Tabulated value
Sample A	8	4.4	19.59	-0.2	14	2.086
Sample B	3.05	1.78	3.16	0.387	5	

Degree of Freedom ,df= 21-1= 20

t1 + t2= 0.187

The tabulated value of t for 20 df at 5 % level of significance for two tailed test is 2.086

since the calculated value t i.e 0.187, is less than the tabulated value of t, hence Null hypothesis may be accepted at 5 % level of significance.

Findings

1. During the survey it was found that people are not aware about the basic drafts of the policy which forms as a basic general knowledge for academicians. A study conducted in through Random sampling in an university resulted into less than 50% of the people are aware about the same.
2. It targets to achieve the 100% Gross Enrolment ratio by 2030.
3. Due to its tri language approach it has given importance to the diverse culture and language of India and also it would break the stereotype, language is not the matter of knowledge. It has provided an option for the students to study Sanskrit and other ancient languages.
4. During the survey it was found that people are not aware about the basic drafts of the policy which forms as a basic general knowledge for academicians.
5. Focusing on the physical education, subjects such as yoga, music, dance and horticulture, sculptors would make the child proficient from the childhood.
6. The new education policy has four steps, Foundation stage, preparatory stage, Middle stage and secondary stage.
7. National educational technological farm will be formed to promote digital education to cater the need of E- education of both school and higher education.

8. Assessment and Evaluation : The NEP 2020 proposes a shift towards a competency-based approach to assessment and evaluation, which is a positive step towards promoting holistic development and reducing rote learning.

9. Teacher Training and Development: The policy's focus on continuous professional development and multi-disciplinary training for teachers, which is a positive step taken under the policy.

10. Multilingualism: The NEP 2020 emphasizes the importance of vocational education and skill development, which is a positive step towards addressing the employability challenges in India.

Conclusion

The NEP 2020 has been approved by the Government of India and intends to change the entire Indian education system to meet the needs of 21st century effectively and efficiently, it will be implemented successfully in coming years and will surely bring the India on the map of merit countries gain, with aim to provide universalize pre- primary education to all and higher education to all, it has made amendments in the Right to Education Act 2009 by extending the age limit ranges from 3 years to 18 years which quite a welcoming step. However it has observed that many academicians and students at university level are yet not fully aware about its basic fundamentals, which need to be taken care by university or colleges to promote and educate its teachers and professors by conducting various National and state level seminars and persuading teachers by nominating them to attend seminars and add special credit for the same.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. In order to cater the need of education and health Asha worker should also be engaged in the Anganwadi program. Anganwadi should be first converted into the kids zone with better infrastructure.
2. For the age group of 8 years and 11 years, bagless education should be promoted by adopting moral stories as the way of educating children.
3. Internships which have been introduced in the early schooling which is given through the vocational training should be in various areas of our country to make the child aware about its geographical status and environment.
4. In order to promote the concept of employment education the 50% of the evaluation should be made on the basis of local arts promotion culture and small cottage industry.
5. To fulfil the gap between the skill education and job availability, government should also take initiative to ensure an optimum job opportunity available for college pass outs in different streams.
6. It is also recommended to spend more on R & D (Research and development) as compared to other countries, India has allotted very less budget for the same.
7. Since the new policy has put more emphasis on the sports, R&D and culture , government should arrange the funds for the universities to create the basic infrastructure for successful implementation of such plans.
8. Both the central and state government should shake hands to increase the Gross enrolment ratio by providing special packages to the universities.

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